

МЕДИЦИНА, ПЕДАГОГИКА И ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ: ТЕОРИЯ И ПРАКТИКА

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IJTIMOIY-GUMANITAR FANLARNING DOLZARB MASALALARI

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Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda ijtimoiy gumanitar fanlarni o'qitish, tanqidiy fikrlash, ijtimoiy fanlarni qay darajada o'qitish muammosi yosh avlodni yuksak ma'naviyat ruhida tarbiyalash jamiyat oldidagi eng mas'uliyatli va eng dolzarb masala bo'lmoqda.

Kalit sozlar: Ma'naviy yetuklik, tarix, ma'naviyat, ijodiy fikrlash.

ДОЛЗАРБ ВОПРОСЫ СОЦИАЛЬНЫХ И ГУМАНИТАРНЫХ НАУК

Аннотация: Сегодня проблема преподавания социально-гуманитарных наук, критического мышления, а также степени преподавания социальных наук является наиболее ответственным и актуальным вопросом для общества.

Ключевые слова: Духовная зрелость, история, духовность, творческое мышление.

DOLZARB ISSUES OF SOCIAL AND HUMANITARIAN SCIENCES

Annotation: Today, the problem of teaching social humanities, critical thinking, and the extent to which social sciences are taught is the most responsible and urgent issue for the society.

Keywords: Spiritual maturity, history, spirituality, creative thinking.

Inson hayotda o'z o'rnini topishi uchun ijtimoiy fanlarning o'rni beqiyos. XX-XXI asrni ilm-fan taraqqiyoti va axborot-interneti asri deyish mumkin. XXI-asr internet asri eng yuqori cho'qqiga chiqqan asr desak ham bo'ladi. Ammo XX-asrda ilm-fanda ko'plab ixtirolar kashf qilindi, siyosat olami ham yuksak cho'qqiga chiqdi. XX-asrning xalqimizga bergan eng kata in'omi O'zbekiston davlati mustaqilligi bo'ldi. Chunki mustaqillikka erishish yo'lida minglab insonlar o'z jonlarini qurbon qildilar. Mustaqillik xalqimiz eng ezgu orzu armoni edi. Endi

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yangi jamiyat qurish kelajak avlodning ma'naviy dunyosiga bog'liq. Yosh avlodda milliy g'oya, yuksak ma'naviyat, milliy ong, sog'lom fikrni shakllantirish, Vatan taqdiri uchun g'oyaviy kurashchanlik ruhida tarbiyalashda, komil inson bo'lib shakllantirishda ijtimoiy fanlarni, O'zbekiston tarixi fanining o'rni katta. Qancha mashaqqatlar ila qo'lga kiritilgan milliy davlat mustaqilligini saqlab qolish, uni kelajaki buyuk davlat qilib barpo etish juda ham sharafli vazifa. Va bunday sharafli vazifani bajarilishi milliy ma'naviyatga, milliy dunyoqarashga bog'liq. Yosh avlodaga o'z ona tilini, Ona Vatani tarixini anglatmasdan tarixiy bilim va tarbiya bermasdan, ularning ongida milliy o'zlikni, vatanparvarlik, milliy bundkor g'oyalarni shakllantirish mumkin emas. albatta har bir yosh avlod oldida bunday sharafli burch turadi va uni ado etish uchun avvalambor ularga ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarni o'rgatish har qachongidan ham mas'uliyatli vazifa hisoblanadi. "O'z tarixini bilmaydigan, kechagi kunini unutgan millatning kelajaki yo'q. Bizning qadimiy va go'zal diyorumiz, nafaqat sharq, balki jahon sivilizatsiyasi beshiklaridan biri bo'lganini xalqaro jamoatchilik tan olmoqda va e'tirof etmoqda. Bu tabarruk zamindan ne-ne buyuk zotlar, olimu-ulamolar, siyosatchi va sarkardalar yetishib chiqqanini, umumbshariy madaniyatning uzviy qismiga aylanib ketgan dunyoviy va diniy ilmlarning ayniqsa, islom dini bilan bog'liq bilimlarning tarixan eng yuqori bosqichga ko'tarilishida ona yurtimizda tug'ulib kamolga yetgan ulug' allomalarning o'rni beqiyos ekan bizga ulkan g'urur va iftixor bag'ishlaydi" deydi Birinchi Prezidentimiz Islom Abdug'aniyevich Karimov o'zining "Tarixiy xotirasiz kelajak yo'q asarida." Bugun bizning oldimizdagi eng dolzarb va davr taqazosi bo'lgan masala ta'lim tizimida yoshlarga "Vatan tarixini" asosiy fan sifatida o'qitishdir. Bundan kelib chiqadiki ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarni o'qitishdan asosiy maqsad; o'tmishli tariximizni, kechagi kunimizni, kim bo'ganimizu kim bo'lmoqchi ekanimizni, kimlarning avlodi va kimlarning kelajaki ekanimizni bilmasdan turib buyuk kelajak barpo eta olmaymiz. Biz avvalo yosh avlod ongiga xalqimizning bugungi istiqloli uchun olib borilgan necha asrlik kurash, mustaqillikning qanchalar ulug' ne'mat ekanligini singdirib, ular qalbida insoniylik, vatanparvarlik, sadoqat, mehr-muhabbat, burch va mas'uliyat tuyg'ularini singdirishda "Falsafa", "Milliy istiqlol g'oyasi", "Ma'naviyatshunoslik", "Tarix" kabi ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarning ahamiyati nihoyatda kata. Bu fanlar yosh avlodni xalqimizning milliy qadriyatlari, halollik, poklik, mehantsevarlik, rostgo'ylik, insonparvarlik, kamtarinlik, iymon-e'tiqod ruhida tarbiyalaydi. Vatan

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va xalq oldidagi burchlarini o'rgatadi. Ijtimoiy fanlar kelajak avlod hayotida muhim hisblanib, ularni kreativ fikrlashga undaydi, Jamiyat hayotidagi o'zgarishlarga befarq qolmasdan faol ishtirok etishga chorlaydi. Ma'naviyatini yuksaltirib, diniy ekstrimizim va terrorizm kabi yot va zararli g'oyalar tahdidiga tushmaslikni ularga qarshi qay usulda kurashish kerakligini o'rgatadi. Nutq rivojlanishiga ta'sir ko'rsatadi, nutqiy boylik ortib, siyosiy yetuklik, oshib boradi. Ijtimoiy fanlar davlat siyosati darajasidagi masalalar bo'lib u yosh avlodni hayotdagi turfa jarayonlarni anglashga o'rgatuvchi kuchli motivatsiya bo'lib xizmat qiladi.

Prezidentimiz Shavkat Mirziyoyev ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlar masalasiga t'xtalib o'tar ekan o'zining 2021-yil chop etilgan "Yangi O'zbekiston strategiyasi" kitobida shunday deydi; "Milliy ma'naviyatimizni rivojlantirish uni xalqimiz, ayniqsa, yoshlarimiz hayotiga singdirishda ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarning ahamiyati juda kata. Afsus bu fanlar rivoji zamondan ortda qolmoqda. Xususan biz nihoyatda dolzarb bo'lgan tarix fani ham bundan mustasno emas. Tarixga oid ilmiy tadqiqot ishlari asosan bayonchilik, publitsistik usulda olib borilmoqda. Natijada olis va yaqin o'tmishimizdagi ko'pgina voqealar mohiyati, ularni yuzaga keltirgan omillar va tarixiy qonuniyatlar ochilmasdan qolmoqda. Biz avvalambor yoshlarni tarixdan saboq olib, xulosa chiqarishga o'rgatishimiz, ularni tarix ilmi bilan qurollantirishimiz, milliy tarixni milliy ruh bilan yaratishimiz kerakligini aks holda uning tarbiyaviy ahamiyati qolmasligini chuqurroq anglatishimiz va bilmog'imiz kerak "deya takidlaydi.

➤ Ijtimoiy-gumanitarfanlar insonga tafakkurni shakllantirishda hayotda o'z o'rini topib, insonga, davlatga, jamiyatga bo'lgan munosabatini kreativ jihatdan boyitishda katta yordam beradi. Tan olishimiz kerakki bugungi kunda jamiyatimizdagi o'zgarishlarga nisbatan loqaydlik hissi yuqori bo'lgan beparvolik kabi illatlarni o'ziga kasb qilib olayotgan insonlar oramizda borligi achinarli holat. Ularda ma'naviy komillik, ma'naviy ong shakillanmaganligini ko'rishimiz mumkin. Bu kabi illatlar har birimizni tashvishga solishi kerak. Chunki bu holatlar ma'naviy ruhiyatga, ijtimoiy kayfiyatga, aholi orasida ijtimoiy hayotga ta'siri zararli bo'lib ijtimoiy-ma'naviy va ma'naviy muhitning buzilishiga sabab bo'ladi. Jamiyatda ro'y berayotgan yomon illatlar yolg'onchilik, firibgarlik, o'g'irilik, qalloblik, giyohvandlik, johillik, din niqobi, odam savdosi tobora ortib borayotganligi insonlar qalbi va ongida ma'naviy bo'shliq borligidan dalolat beradi. Anashunday insonlar

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ongida ma'naviy bo'shliqning oldini olishda ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarning o'rni benihoya yuksakdir.

➤ Aniq fanlar o'z o'quvchilariga ko'zlangan maqsadlarga yetishish uchun formulaga tayangan holda masalaning yechimini yechishga yordam beradi.

➤ Tabiiy fanlar bo'lsa o'z o'quvchilariga aniq tasdiqlangan, isbotlangan ma'lumotlar asosida ish ko'rib maqsadga yetishishni o'rgatadi.

Ammo bulardan farqli ravishda ijtimoiy-gumanitar nafaqat o'quvchilarga balki, butun insoniyatga, jamiyatning har bir a'zosiga insoniylikni, halollik kabi insoniy fa'zilatlarini o'rgatadi. Insoniyat yaralibdiki unda ezgulik va yovuzlik, bunyodkor va vayronakor g'oyalar bir-biriga qarama qarshi kurashib keladi. Garchi yakunida ezgulik g'alaba qozonishini bilsada ammo bunga osonlikcha erishib bo'lmaydi. Bunda shunday xulosa qilishimiz mumkinki, ijtimoiy-gumanitar sohaning qay darajada murakkabligi jamiyat hayotidagi o'rni beqiyosdir. Ijtimoiy-gumanitar soha bu shunchaki kimningdir xohishiga qarab o'rganiladigan soha emas, balki, jamiyat hayotida yuksak o'rin egallovchi real zarur soha.

Ayniqsa bugungi kunda texnika glaballashuvi, raqamli texnologiyalar, internet rivojlangan zamonda insonning insonga bo'lgan mehr-oqibati yo'qolib, bir-biridan uzoqlashayotganligi, inonlar electron resurslar bilan vaqt o'tkazib ular bilan ehtiyojlarini qondirayotganligiga guvoh bo'lmoqdamiz. To'g'ri XXI-asr texnika taraqqiyoti cho'qqisi yuksak rivojlanishi ijobiy holat. Ammo jamiyatni texnik texnologiyalar bilan chegaralab qo'yish insonni ijtimoiylashuviga to'sqinlik qiladi. Bugun biz ga'rb mamalakatlarida texnika va tabiiy sohalar orqali rivojlanishga intilib, insoniylikni unutayotgan ma'naviyat va ma'rifatdadan uzoqlashayotgan, hamma narsani moddiy boyliklarda hisoblayotgan, faqat o'z manfaatlarini o'ylab xalqini jar yoqasiga yetaklayotgan, odob-axloq va ma'naviy go'zallikdan ko'ra tana go'zalligini ustun qo'yayotgan xalqlarni insonlarni uchratishimiz juda achinarli. Bularning hammasi ularda ijtimoiy-gumanitar sohadagi islohotlar insonlarning yurag-yuragiga qon-qoniga singmaganidan desak mubolag'a bo'lmaydi va odob-axloq ma'naviyat kabi inson ruhiyatiga ijobiy ta'sir ko'rsatuvchi kuchlarning o'z o'rnini yo'qotib borishidir.

Xulosa o'rnida shuni aytishimiz mumkinki; ijtimoiy-gumanitar sohaning zaiflashuvi jamiyatda gumanitar muammolarni keltirib chiqaradi. Bu esa insoniyat hayotida fojeali oqibatlarni keltirib chiqradi. Yoshlarning aholi orasida, ayniqsa, endi shakllanib kelayotgan yoshlar orasida turli yot va zararli g'oyalarga ergashib,

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aldanib qolayotganliklari ijtimoiy-gumanitar sohada kamchiliklar borligidan dalolat beradi Ma'naviyatli, tafakkuri keng, dumyoqarashi boy xalq hech qachon tanazzulga yuz tutmaydi. Ijtimoiy-gumanitar fanlarning o'qitilishi jamiyatning rivojiga ta'sir qiluvchi salbiy illatlarni oldini olishga xizmat qiladi. Zero bunday xalqning tarixi buyuk, ma'naviyati yuksak, kelajaki porloq bo'ladi.

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